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Historical Sciences

A TRUE SUCCESSOR OF GREAT CENTRAL ASIAN SCHOLARS

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Abstract

The study analyzed the life and scientific activities of the famous Arabist-Islamic scholar, doctor of historical Sciences, Professor Ubaydulla Uvatov, and his contribution to the study of the scientific heritage of Central Asian scientists. In particular, the role of the scientist in the study of the scientific heritage of Amir Temur, Imam Termezi, Hakim Termezi, Abul Muin Nasafi, Mahmud Zamakhshari was revealed. The main problems faced by Ubaydulla Uvatov in studying the legacy of these scientists and statesmen were discussed. The author reveals the role of the scientist in the development of Islamic culture and science in Uzbekistan, the importance of studying human nature, and highlights his worthy contribution to the international spread of the religion of Islam.

Keywords: Islam, Ubaydulla Uvatov, source studies, Amir Temur, Mahmud Zamakhshari, Imam Termezi, Hakim Termezi.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, along with all aspects of public life, great reforms have been carried out in the field of religion and enlightenment. Professor Ubaydulla Uvatov, who is devoting all his efforts to the study of the sacred religion of Islam, the restoration of ancestral heritage and their transmission to future generations, is actively working to educate the younger generation in the spirit of peace, humanity, tolerance and solidarity. The work of Orientalist, Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor Ubaydulla Uvatov on the restoration and preservation of national and religious values, the study and promotion of the rich scientific heritage of our great scholars and thinkers, as well as strengthening the atmosphere of religious tolerance in society is noteworthy. Ubaydulla Uvatov gave lectures in foreign languages about the unprecedented contribution of Central Asian scholars to world civilization not only in our country and Central Asia, but also in the world, as well as in the UAE, Russia, Britain, Kazakhstan, Turkey, Egypt, Saudi Arabia and other countries. It is worth noting that his lectures in foreign countries will bring great pride to Uzbek people. We know and appreciate Ubaydulla Uvatov as an invaluable heritage of our learned ancestors and a tireless promoter of spirituality and enlightenment.

The scientist makes a worthy contribution to the development of Islamic culture and science in Uzbekistan, the study of the human nature and noble ideas of sacred religion, the invaluable scientific heritage of Central Asian great scholars and thinkers and their widespread international promotion.

In particular, Ubaydulla Uvatov's contribution to the study of the scientific heritage of Termez scientists is invaluable. During the years of independence, Ubaydulla Uvatov was one of the first to study and promote the scientific heritage of Imam Moturidi [1], Imam Termezi [2], Hakim Termezi [3], Abul Muin Nasafi [4], Mahmud Zamakhshari [5] and other scholars.

II. METHODOLOGY

The article uses chronological data, systematic periodic data, comparative and quantitative methods, and previous researches. About twenty scientific on the the life and works of Ubaydulla Uvatov are used to explain "A true successor of great central asian scholars". Besides that, the researcher had used journals and articles to collect data related to the research.

III. DISCUSSION

Ubaydulla Uvatov was born on February 23, 1940 in the village of Pachkamar, Guzar district, Kashkadarya region, in a family of cattle breeders. In 1964 he graduated from the Faculty of Oriental Studies of the Central Asian State University, Department of Arabic Philology with a degree in Oriental Studies, Arabic Philology. From 1964 he worked as a teacher at the Faculty of Oriental Studies of Tashkent State University. He also worked as an Arabic translator in the Arab Republic of Egypt in 1962-1963, the State of Iraq in 1966-1967 and 1975-1978, and the Libyan People's Republic in 1982-1985.

In 1967-1970, Uvatov studied at the graduate school of the Institute of Oriental Studies named after Abu Rayhon Beruni of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan. On April 12, 1974, he defended his dissertation on "Translation and scientific analysis of Ibn Arabshah's work" *Ajaib al-maqdur fi tarikhi Taymur* "(Miracles of Destiny in the History of Timur)."

On April 12, 1974, Uvatov successfully defended his dissertation at the Institute of Oriental Studies named after Abu Rayhon Beruni of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan.

The famous artist Malik Nabiev, who won the competition for the creation of a true portrait of Amir Temur in 1996 on the occasion of the 660th anniversary of Amir Temur, also used the translation of Ibn Arabshah's work to create a popular portrait of Amir Temur. From the first years of independence, U. Uvatov continued to hold responsible positions in the highest organizations of the republic. In particular, from 1991 to 1992 he served as head of the advisory sector of the Office of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, from 1992 to 1995 as First Deputy Chairman of the Committee on Religious Affairs under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In 1995-1997 he worked as a leading researcher at the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, in 1997-1999 as the First Deputy Chairman of the International Amir Temur Foundation, in 1999-2000 as the First Deputy Chairman of the International Charitable Foundation "Golden Heritage".

His fluency in Arabic and his ability to work with historical sources have made him famous in the Islamic world. U.Uvatov was one of the first to publish scientific and educational pamphlets in Uzbek about Imam Bukhari [7], Imam Termezi, Hakim Termezi, Imam Moturidi, Mahmud Zamakhshari, Abul Muin Nasafi, Lomishi [8] and many other scholars from Central Asia. Ubaydulla Uvatov has continued this work to this day, and his work has served as the basis for the book "Scientists of the Great Country", which contains valuable information about the life, work and scientific heritage of 70 scientists who grew up in our sacred land.

U.Uvatov again addressed the topic of the heritage of our ancestors, and on June 16, 2002 at the Tashkent Islamic University defended his doctoral dissertation on "The role of scholars of Movarounnahr and Khorasan in the development of hadith (al-Bukhari, Muslim, al-Termezi)". At the same time, U.Uvatov, who has been working at the Islamic Studies Research Center of Tashkent Islamic University since 1999, and later at the Department of Sources, has conducted effective research with young people and has supervised dozens of 20 master's theses and dissertations.

During his scientific career, Uvatov has prepared more than 300 articles, about 50 books and pamphlets.

Ubaydulla Uvatov is a courageous historian who researched Amir Temur in difficult times, a true successor of great scholars, a passionate coach, a devoted teacher who introduced the names of Uzbek ancestors and his unique creative work not only in Uzbekistan but around the world.

Through the works of U.Uvatov, the Uzbek people learned in Uzbek about Imam Bukhari, Imam Termezi, Hakim Termezi, Imam Moturidi, Mahmud Zamakhshari, Abul Muin Nasafi, Lomishi and many other scholars who grew up in Uzbekistan and their invaluable written heritage.

In Uzbek Islamic studies and source studies, Ubaydulla Uvatov is portrayed as a "pioneer", that is, an attempt to discover new scientific topics.

IV. RESULTS

Since 1988, Ubaydulla Uvatov has translated samples of Imam Termezi's hadiths into Uzbek. These translations have been published in newspapers and magazines such as Sharq Yulduzi and Tashkent Oqshomi. He was one of the main initiators of the celebration of the 1200th anniversary of the birth of Imam Termezi in 1990. In their own words, the study of the life and work of the scholars of religion began with Imam Tirmidhi. Independence provided ample opportunities for the restoration of the sacred names of scholars, the study of their works. U. Uvatov also wrote for Hakim Termizi and Abu Isa Termizi.

In particular:

1. In 1993, he presented a translation of Imam al-Tirmidhi's book, Ash-Shamoil an-Nabawiyya, to readers.
2. In 2001, he wrote a pamphlet entitled Al-Hakim at-Termezi (Life and Legacy), which provided a basic outline of the life and work of Hakim Termezi.
3. The dissertation entitled "The role of the scholars of Mavaraunnahr and Khurasan in the development of the science of hadith (Al-Bukhari, Muslim, At-Termezi), defended in 2002, led the teacher to become the only hadith scholar [11].
4. In 2005 he published the first pamphlet "Two great sages" dedicated to Hakim Termizi and Abu Isa Termizi.
5. In 2014, the "Collection of Scholars of our country" was published, in which U. Uvatov's "Abu Isa Muhammad Termizi, Abul Abbas Mustagfiriy Nasafiy, Imam Bukhari" articles were published.
6. In the book "Two great sages: the life of the famous muhaddith Abu Isa at-Termizi and the great thinker Al-Hakim at-Termizi" published in 2005, the information published in 2005 was supplemented and presented to the public in an expanded form.
7. In the collection of materials of the Republican scientific-theoretical conference "The legacy of Termez scholars and thinkers and its role in raising the spirituality of our people" held in 2016, the teacher's article "Al-Jami 'as-sahih - the masterpiece of Imam al-Termizi" was presented.

He has been a prolific creator in various fields of source studies. Many scholars know Ubaydulla Uvatov as a scholar of Mahmud Zamakhshari's works. In Ubaydulla Uvatov's "Delicate Phrases" the author gives information about the life and scientific work of Mahmud Zamakhshari. At the end of the book there is an Uzbek translation of "Delicate Phrases".

The scholar, who was fluent in Arabic language and literature, translated the text of the work into Uzbek smoothly, and the book was published. In addition, he published a large-scale article on "Life and scientific heritage of Mahmud Zamakhshari" in the collection "The great scholar of Khorezm" published in 1998. Also, in 2006 in the publishing house "Yangi asr avlodi" the scientist wrote the book "The great scientist from Khorezm. Mahmud Zamakhshari: The book Nawabig al-Kalim has been published. This is a collection of articles by Ubaydulla Murodovich dedicated to Mahmud Zamakhshari and written in different years. His articles "Zamakhshar - my homeland", "The only one of his time", "Flower of Creativity", "Life and scientific lessons of the scholar", "Az-Zamakhshari's homeland in medieval Arabic sources", as well as the works of Arab scholar Sheikh Muhammad Abu Zahra The article "Az-Zamakhshari genius" and the Uzbek translation of "Navobig al-kalim" are included. He has also published articles on Mahmud Zamakhshari in collections dedicated to scholars.

Ubaydulla Uvatov showed great courage in restoring the truth about the personality and activities of Amir Temur. It is no exaggeration to say that this was one of the age-old aspirations of Uzbek people. The fact that most of the sources dedicated to Amir Temur, created in the Middle Ages, were written in Persian and were well known to the scientific community, drew the attention of the young Arabist to the Arabic sources dedicated to this universal figure. Among these 50 sources, Ibn Arabshah's 15th-century work *Ajoib al-Maqdur fi Tarikhi Taymur* (The Miracles of Destiny in the History of Timur), originally from Sham (Syria) and copied by Amir Temur to Samarkand, has a special place. Suffice it to say that the text of this work was published in Europe in the XVII century by the famous Dutch orientalist, mathematician and astronomer Jacobus Golius (1596-1667), and since then it has been studied by Europeans. The original of Golius' translation of the work, unfortunately, has not been published. According to Academician I. Krachkovsky, this translation was presented to the scholars in a low-quality French statement made in 1658. In general, according to the eminent scholar mentioned, Ibn Arabshah's work "... was not understood by any historian who knew Arabic on average because of the extreme complexity and silence of its language."

Uvatov's work was such a difficult task as translating into Uzbek and researching a work that had already attracted the attention of the European scientific community and had maintained its status as one of the most important original sources on Amir Temur for centuries. The interest in Ibn Arabshah's work on Amir Temur was so great in the West that in 1778 it was included as a separate section in a special dictionary published by Willmet, along with the authority of the Qur'an and al-Hariri. The young arabist U.Uvatov, who knew that Ibn Arabshah's work was published several times in Calcutta and Cairo in the XIX-XX centuries, became even more interested in him. Therefore, as soon as the researcher arrived in Egypt in 1962, they set out in search of the ancient manuscript of the work, and soon found one of them. Since then, "Ajaib al-Maqdur fi Tarikhi Taymur" has taken its permanent place on the researcher's desk and has never left it. Thanks to many years of hard work, the work was fully translated into Uzbek, and the translator wrote about 1,400 scientific commentaries.

Although Uvatov's research was defended as a candidate's dissertation in 1974, its full text was published only in 1992, during the period of independence. The hidden secrets behind this chronology are well known to older intellectuals who are aware of the peculiarities of Soviet ideology. It should be noted that this work is due to certain reasons, but also due to the author's conflicting personal feelings for Sahibkiran, because his family did not move to Samarkand voluntarily, of course, it was written in a somewhat critical spirit towards Amir Temur. But even so, the information contained in it is extremely diverse, rich, and objective, and this source has earned the trust of researchers around the world. The information about the life and work of Amir Temur, reflected in it, is so diverse and rich that there are few sources who can argue with this inscription. In particular, the information presented in the play, which reveals the human qualities of Sahibkiran, respect for scientists, justice, military potential, appearance and other aspects, is more perfect than any other source. Let us pay attention to the description of the image of great ancestor quoted by Ibn Arabshah: "Timur was tall, erect, as if he was a descendant of ancient heroes, broad-foreheaded, big-headed, very strong and powerful, magnificent, white-red face but spotless, not wheat-colored, arms and legs strong, shoulders broad, fingers thick, feet fat, tall, bald,

right limbs crippled and paralyzed, two eyes lightly two candles, joy unknown, was thick-voiced; He was not afraid of death, and although he was eighty years old, he was painless, calm, full-bodied and mature, as hard as a dense (thick) stone ... ”

It should be noted that at a time when efforts were being made to revive the image of Amir Temur as a savage, ignorant and bloodthirsty person, the dissemination of such information was not only important in the sense of restoring justice, but also scientific heroism. So far, such behavior has had to be held accountable before the appropriate authorities. But such courage of the scientist justified itself.

A scientifically based truth about the image of Amir Temur began to form in the public. One of the proofs of this conclusion is that the portrait of Sahibkiran, created by the People's Artist of Uzbekistan Malik Nabiev, is based primarily on the description given in the book of Ibn Arabshah. As part of the celebrations of the 660th anniversary of the birth of Amir Temur, he was confirmed by a special panel as a true official appearance of Sahibkiran.

V. CONCLUSION

Well-known Arabist-Islamic scholar, Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor U.Uvatov is distinguished by the breadth, effective use of resources and originality. Ubaydulla Uvatov has been working hard in studying the life and scientific heritage of many scholars from Central Asia, such as Abdullah ibn Mubarak Marwazi, Imam Bukhari, Imam Darimi, Imam Termezi, Hakim Termezi, Abul Muin Nasafi, Imam Moturidi, Mahmud Zamakhshari, Abdukholik Gijduvani, etc. The scientist makes a worthy contribution to the development of Islamic culture and science in Uzbekistan, the study of the human nature and noble ideas of the holy religion of Islam, the invaluable scientific heritage of great scholars and thinkers and their widespread dissemination at the international level. It is also working to ensure the stability of the socio-spiritual environment in society, strengthen interethnic harmony, train mature professionals with a thorough knowledge of religious and secular knowledge, educate the younger generation in the spirit of love, tolerance and respect for national values. U. Uvatov's exemplary life serves as a model for the younger generation.

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ИСТИННЫЙ ПРЕЕМНИК ВЕЛИКИХ УЧЕНЫХ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ

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Аннотация

В исследовании анализировалась жизнь и научная деятельность известного арабиста-исламоведа, доктора исторических наук, профессора Убайдуллы Уватова, а также его вклад в изучение научного наследия ученых Центральной Азии. В частности, была раскрыта роль ученого в изучении научного наследия Амира Темура, имама Термези, Хакима Термези, Абуль Муина Насафи, Махмуда Замахшари. Были обсуждены основные проблемы, с которыми столкнулся Убайдулла Уватов при изучении наследия этих ученых и государственных деятелей. Автор раскрывает роль ученого в развитии исламской культуры и науки в Узбекистане, важность изучения человеческой природы, а также подчеркивает его достойный вклад в международное распространение религии Ислама.

Ключевые слова: Ислам, Убайдулла Уватов, источниковедение, Амир Темур, Махмуд Замахшари, Имам Термези, Хахим Термези.

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